

Supporting Information

Room-temperature Single-molecule Conductance Switch via Confined Coordination-induced Spin-State Manipulation

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Section S1. Scanning tunneling microscope (STM) Break-Junction Experiments in TMB.

Conductance measurements: Conductance measurements were performed using the home-built STM through the break-junction technique to form gold-molecule-gold junctions as previously reported at room temperature. The gold tips were fabricated by carefully cleaned and annealed in flame with Gold wires (99.99%, 0.25mm diameter) which were purchased from Beijing Jiaming Platinum Nonferrous Metal Co, Ltd. All the target solutions were 0.1mM in 1, 3, 5-trimethylbenzene (TMB, 99%, Sigma-Aldrich used as received). Substrate chips were 100nm gold film deposited on the monocrystalline face of a silicon wafer. The gold-coated substrate chips were cleaned by immersion in solution with $V(\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4): V(\text{H}_2\text{O}_2) = 3:1$ more than 2 hours. After that, the substrate chips were boiling in fresh deionised water three times. All the break-junction measurements are carried out with 0.1 V *dc* bias applied between the gold tip and substrate and 20 kHz sampling frequency. After connecting the gold tip with the substrate, through retracting the gold tip, the plateaus around G_0 formed (symbol G_0 is the quantized unit of quantum conductance, which is equal to $2e^2/h$), due to the gold-gold atomic contact. Further retracting the tip, nanogaps will be built, and then the single-molecule would fall into the nanogap to form single-molecule junctions, which exhibit new plateaus in 2D conductance. We collected over 2000 conductance traces for each experiment, to analyze the 1D conductance histograms and 2D conductance-displacement cloud maps, which can help to analyze the construction of the molecule junction. Further information concerning the STM-BJ technique and data analysis is given elsewhere.

The STM tip-substrate distance and junction length measurements were corrected through piezo stretching rate and tip snapback distance. Calibration curves for the STM-BJ distance measurements were obtained from a blank experiment using pure solvent 1, 3, 5-trimethylbenzene (TMB). The 1D and 2D histograms showed direct tunneling after the sharp drop of the last gold-gold atomic contact at the quantum conductance G_0 , free of further plateaus or deviations from a smooth exponential

decay of current with distance. From the tunneling decay constant ($\log [\Delta G/G_0]/\Delta z = -5.5 \text{ nm}^{-1}$), (39) the relative displacement distribution in the conductance range from $10^{-3.5} G_0$ to $10^{-5.5} G_0$ was calibrated at 0.36 nm, as shown in the inset of Figure S4. By calibrating the relative distance distribution from $10^{-3.5} G_0$ to $10^{-5.5} G_0$ to 0.36 nm, the stretching rate was determined and used for further statistical analysis of the 2D conductance histograms and the relative displacement distributions of the molecular junctions.^[1]

For the reversible experiments, we first prepared a high concentration solution in TMB (1 mM). Excess of CF_3COOH was added into NiTPPF-2 sample to completely protonate the 3, 5-Lutidine. After that, deionized water was used to wash the solution three times to remove the protonated 3, 5-Lutidine and excess CF_3COOH . When we measured the conductance, the solutions were diluted into 0.1 mM with pure TMB.

Figure S1. The picture of home-built STM-BJ equipment.

Figure S2. The blank experiment for pure solvent. (left) The 1D conductance histogram of the blank experiment for pure solvent. (right) 2D conductance versus relative distance (Δz) histogram and the relative displacement distribution histogram determined from the conductance range between $10^{-3.5} G_0$ to $10^{-5.5} G_0$.

Figure S3. The high conductance state of the NiTPPF system in TMB solution. (a) Contact geometries for the high conductance state of NiTPPF molecule; (b-f) 1D conductance histograms, the 2D conductance-displacement cloud maps of high conductance parts from STM-BJ experiment of NiTPPF, NiTPPF-1, and NiTPPF-2 in TMB solution under 0.1 V bias, respectively. The high conductance is close to

$10^{-4.1} G_0$.

Figure S4. The low conductance state of the NiTPPF system in TMB solution. (a), Logarithmically binned conductance histograms of NiTPPF, NiTPPF-1, and NiTPPF-2 in TMB solution, respectively. Inset: Individual conductance traces measured in solutions of NiTPPF, NiTPPF-1 and NiTPPF-2 at 0.1V, respectively. (b, c, d) 2D conductance histograms generated from conductance traces measured at 0.1V for NiTPPF, NiTPPF-1 and NiTPPF-2, respectively. Inset: the plateau length of NiTPPF, NiTPPF-1 and NiTPPF-2, respectively.

Figure S5. Single-molecule conductance measurements of the ZnTPPF system in TMB solution. 1D conductance histograms and 2D conductance-displacement cloud maps from the STM-BJ experiment of **ZnTPPF**, **ZnTPPF-1**, and **ZnTPPF-2** in TMB solution under 0.1 V bias without selection, respectively.

Section S2. The ensemble characterization

NMR titration. Each ^1H NMR tube was filled with 0.2 mL of a **NiTPPF** solution (10.0mmol/L) in toluene- d_8 (Figure S6). Then different amounts of a solution of ligands in toluene- d_8 (10 vol%) were added and the tubes were filled up to 0.3 mL with toluene- d_8 and sealed. We measured five different ligand concentration solutions (0.2 mmol/L, 0.4 mmol/L, 0.6 mmol/L, 0.8 mmol/L and 1.0 mmol/L)

Figure S6. ¹H NMR of NiTPPF system in toluene. ¹H NMR (400 MHz, toluene-d₈, 298 K, tetramethylsilane) signals of the β pyrrole protons of NiTPPF. The chemical shifts are located in ~8.8 and 8.5 ppm. ¹H NMR (400 MHz, 10 mmol/L in toluene-d₈, 298 K, tetramethylsilane) signals of the β pyrrole protons of NiTPPF shift to larger ppm value after adding 3, 5-Lutidine from 0 M to 1.0 M.

Figure S7. UV/Vis spectra of NiTPPF as a function of 3, 5-Lutidine. (Left) The band of pure NiTPPF (415 nm) decreases and a new band arises at 429 nm upon addition of 3, 5-Lutidine. The spectra were collected from a 2×10^{-5} mol/L of NiTPPF in toluene solvent. (Right) The equilibrium constants derived from UV-Vis titration experiments in ensemble solution: $K_1 = 0.92 \pm 0.03$ L/mol, $K_2 = 4.83 \pm 0.2$ L/mol.

UV-Vis titration. 3.0 mL of a 2×10^{-5} mol/L of NiTPPF in toluene solvent at 32°C was titrated with 3, 5-Lutidine (L). The absorption was measured at the Soret band of uncomplexed NiTPPF (λ_{\max} 415 nm) at 12 different concentrations of 3, 5-Lutidine from 0 to 0.84 mol L⁻¹(see Figure S2)

The concentration of both paramagnetic species can be derived as follows:

$$c_{para} = c_{NiTPPF \cdot (L)} + c_{NiTPPF \cdot (L)_2} = c_0 - c_{NiTPPF} = \frac{\varepsilon_{NiTPPF} \cdot c_0 - a_{NiTPPF}}{\varepsilon_{NiTPPF}} \quad (1)$$

Where c_{para} is the sum of the concentrations of all paramagnetic complexes $NiTPPF \cdot (L)$ and $NiTPPF \cdot (L)_2$. ε_{NiTPPF} is the extinction coefficient of $NiTPPF$, c_0 is the initial concentration of $NiTPPF$, a_{NiTPPF} is the absorption of $NiTPPF$ at 416 nm. According to the coordination reaction as followed:

When the reaction reaches chemical equilibrium, we obtain $K_1 = \frac{c_{NiTPPF \cdot (L)}}{c_{NiTPPF} \cdot c_L}$ (2) and

$$K_2 = \frac{c_{NiTPPF \cdot (L)_2}}{c_{NiTPPF \cdot (L)} \cdot c_L} \quad (3), \text{ where } c_L \text{ is the concentration of 3, 5-Lutidine.}$$

Combined function 2, we obtain $\frac{c_{para}}{c_{NiTPPF} \cdot c_L} = K_1 + K_1 K_2 \cdot c_L$, indicating that the plot

of $\frac{c_{para}}{c_{NiTPPF} \cdot c_L}$ vs c_L should exhibit a linear relationship. The intercept corresponds to

K_1 and the slope defines $(K_1 \cdot K_2)$.

Figure S8. UV/Vis spectra of NiTPPF as a function of pyridine. (Left) The band of pure $NiTPPF$ (415 nm) decreases and a new band arises at 431 nm upon addition of Pyridine. The spectra were collected from a 2×10^{-5} mol/L of $NiTPPF$ in toluene solvent. (Right) The equilibrium constants derived from UV-Vis titration experiments in ensemble solution: $K_1 = 0.13 \pm 0.02$ L/mol, $K_2 = 3.2 \pm 0.3$ L/mol.